

Constructing Virtual Narrative Environments: A Surrealist Exploration of 17th-Century European Oriental Fantasies

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to construct interactive narratives in virtual reality that incorporate multiple art forms and explore various contexts. Through literature review and historical research, the theoretical analysis of surreal aesthetics is conducted to recreate 17th-century European fascination with the distant and mysterious Orient in a virtual environment. The paper describes the process of constructing a virtual reality space, including context-specific worldviews, interaction mechanisms, and artistic elements. Following a technical evaluation of the initial interactive prototype, the project proposes a virtual reality game, aiming to provide an immersive interactive experience that enhances sensory engagement through physical device control.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Human-centered computing** → **Virtual reality**.

KEYWORDS

Virtual Reality, Surrealism, 17th-century European fascination, Interactive narratives

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1 INTRODUCTION

The project presents a utopian Oriental VR world, portraying the experiences of a 17th-century Italian Jesuit travelling through China. Players will immerse themselves in an art style that subverts reality, utilising an orrery, a physical Earth-Moon Rotation device that serves as the key to exploring the contents of this diary.

In the game, players have the capability to interact with the orrery, which is a physical Earth-Moon Rotation System device, enabling them to adjust the position and phase of the moon within the virtual reality environment. Through the movement of the moon, players' visualisation of the external scenery outside the window will be heightened. Enigmatic windows will materialize as the moon traverses specific areas, providing panoramic views that encompass the player's surroundings. By controlling the moon's journey between these windows, players can prompt scene transitions. They will discover clues within the depicted scenes, gradually unveiling the missionary's narrative in the East.

Concurrently, the game's narrative invites the player to gain insight into 17th-century European fascination with China, providing a critical exploration of ancient Eastern elements and their historical significance. This approach offers the player an immersive entry into the space and a firsthand encounter with the surreal ambiance and narrative of virtual reality.

2 THE 17TH TO 18TH CENTURY EUROPEAN DREAM OF CHINA

In the 17th and 18th centuries, Europe was enthralled by a fervent fascination with the Orient, an intense admiration for the mystery and allure of the Far East that permeated European society. Eastern regions' cultures, arts, and philosophies, such as China, India and Persia[10], began to evoke widespread interest and imitation in Europe. More than a mere cultural exchange, the Eastern fantasy of this era was a quest for the unknown, the exotic, and the enigmatic.

As information from the East increasingly reached the West, many European scholars, often without ever visiting the East, began researching it, primarily focusing on their idealised vision of China.

Figure 1: Detail of "sailing coaches", *China Illustrata*, 1671.

Athanasius Kircher, a renowned Jesuit scholar, scientist, and archaeologist of the 17th century, is regarded as one of the foremost China experts of his era due to his extensive study of China [3] and his deep fascination with the Chinese language and culture. Although he never personally visited China, his book "*China Illustrata*" (1667) [5] gained popularity and became one of the most important sources of information about China for Europeans at the time. The book can be seen as a whimsical encyclopedia of the Chinese empire, featuring numerous maps and illustrations that cover various topics, including Chinese landscapes, cities, architecture, flora and fauna, clothing, myths and legends, and cultural practices [12]. These illustrations are regarded as some of China's most comprehensive visual representations from that period. Accounts included descriptions of land vehicles for navigation, birds trained to aid fishermen in catching fish, alluring beauties, flying turtles, and fruits of immense proportions [7]. He also reflected the

perspective of the Jesuits in their missionary work in China in his book, emphasising the Christian elements of Chinese history.

While "China Illustrata" garnered significant attention in its time, it is essential to note that Kircher's descriptions and illustrations contain several misrepresentations and inaccuracies, as he never conducted research in China.

3 NARRATIVE FORMS OF SURREALIST ART

Suggestive interactive elements in VR enable players to explore and strengthen their subconscious thoughts and experiences. By actively engaging with these elements, players can imaginatively contribute to the interpretation and significance of the virtual environment. The narrative form of Surrealist art originates from the belief in the "omnipotence of dreams" and the recognition of the power of the unconscious mind. Inspired by Sigmund Freud's ideas, Surrealists regarded dreams as visual manifestations of hidden thoughts and desires [4].

At the same time, Surrealists were known for their rejection of rigid definitions and constraints of art. They prioritized the subject matter over the style and technique of painting, using the latter as vehicles for expressing inspired thoughts and unconscious creative processes. The specific form of these vehicles was less important than their effectiveness in conveying themes and ideas, a perspective that opens up new possibilities for immersive experiences in VR environments[4].

'Two Children Threatened by a Nightingale' incorporates drawing, writing, collage, and relief techniques[11]. The artwork presents a deep perspective space with a striking linear composition, naturally allowing the classical architecture in the distance to merge with the solid woodblock structures in the foreground. Doors and handles positioned at the edges of the frame invite the player to enter the world depicted within the painting. Max Ernst was known for his expertise in blending various art forms to disrupt rational image interpretations. This approach is a testament to the potential of pioneering innovative artistic techniques in creating immersive environments.

Figure 2: " Two Children Threatened by a Nightingale " Max Ernst, 1924.

Virtual reality enables audiences to immerse themselves in impossible environments, offering designers expanded creative possibilities. The successful release of "Monument Valley" in 2014 exemplified the high viability, visual appeal, and playability achieved

through visual illusions in 3D video games[9]. By pushing boundaries within virtual environments, virtual reality enhances the artistic construction of inconceivable spaces. Interactive illustrator and game designer Daniel Ernst explores the potential of Surrealism in VR with his work titled "The Shoebox Diorama," creating a VR environment that submerges players into unconscious interactions and narratives. These stories unfold within shoeboxes where ordered environments coexist alongside absurd occurrences[8]. In "Blocked in Tetris Apocalypse," a nightmarish scenario unfolds around the famous Tetris game. The audience becomes trapped within a Russian scientist's workspace, helplessly witnessing an impending doomsday as vibrant blocks descend from the sky outside their window. Within this surreal reality, players are not merely playing Tetris but fully immersed in its world.

4 CONSTRUCTING NARRATIVES AND INTERACTIONS IN MULTIPLE CONTEXTS

The project's conceptual framework is centred around the historical realities of 17th-century European Oriental fantasies, which are conveyed through various forms of surrealistic storytelling.

The player will be immersed in a dream world experienced by a European Jesuit missionary who explores his fantasies about ancient China within a fantastical setting. Through this experience, they will gain insight into how Europeans perceived China during the 17th century within their imaginative realm. This context represents a Western interpretation and definition of Chinese culture within its specific cultural context. This cross-cultural perspective is inspired by 'Fragment', a poem by Chinese poet Bian Zhilin[2].

You are standing on a bridge enjoying the view, Someone's watching you from a balcony. The moon adorns your window, You adorn someone else's dream.

Guided by this poem and drawing upon the multiple associations in Surrealist art, the present study explores the intricate relationships and interconnections between individuals and environments[1]. The worldview depicted in 'Moonlit Windows' is metaphorically rich, with two central elements: the 'bright moon' and the 'window'. By skillfully enhancing the positive interplay among these suggestive elements, audiences are encouraged to engage their imagination in interpreting the connotations and meanings of the virtual environment[4].

4.1 Virtual Reality Environments and Narratives

'Moonlit Windows' offers players an immersive watercolour-style visual experience, utilising stylised visuals to transport them into a fantastical period of East-West exchanges. The virtual environment initially presents the beginning of a 17th-century European missionary's journey, set in a Jesuit's studying room. Players are encouraged to explore the room to gain an initial understanding of the missionary's personal traits and historical context. In the monthly weather shorts experienced by the Italian Jesuit, players were immersed in learning about the diverse landscapes he observed through the moonlit windows.

Meanwhile, the moonlight also illuminates the eastern lands. This project presents players with surrealist art-infused scenes of Qing Dynasty Guangzhou ports and towns, featuring prominent

Figure 3: Controlling the Moon in Jesuit's studying room, London, 2023.

locations such as wharves, streets, shops, temples, and ship cabins. Players can explore hidden tea puzzles within the bustling ancient Chinese trade ports in these diverse settings.

The virtual world was constructed in Unity, utilising numerous 3D models combined with watercolour shaders and 2D decals to create the environment. The composition and layout of the scenes incorporate the collage style typical of surrealist art, constructing an immersive 3D Chinese collage space that aligns with the project's context, allowing players to experience the narrative art environment in VR freely.

Figure 4: 3D Environment in the watercolour-style, London, 2023.

4.2 Virtual and Physical Interaction

Within its conceptual framework, 'Moonlit Windows' revolves around the interplay between the moon and windows, propelling the narrative through the collection of diverse letters and interaction with the environment. This project encompasses two fundamental gameplay mechanics[13]: control the moon rotation to illuminate windows and collect letters (of the alphabet) to change the environment.

In order to integrate diverse art forms and subvert rational interpretations of images, the project has developed a physically interactive installation depicting the Earth-Moon rotation, symbolising the product of the European Age of Sail. The design aims to enhance immersion by allowing players to experience changes in place and time within the narrative by manipulating the moon's position and phase using a rotating handle on the Earth-Moon Rotation Device. As the moon passes through a window during this process, it projects light that simulates the Tyndall effect[6]. This visual feedback activates scenes outside the window, enabling players

to traverse different environments. The project uses hand-tracking in VR to offer players a controller-free interaction experience, allowing direct manipulation of objects in virtual and physical spaces. It means players can touch and grab objects in the virtual space with their hands and alter the virtual environment by controlling a physical Orrery. The integration of virtual reality with physical devices aims to provide players with a visual narrative and interactive experience that closely combines surrealist art with specific historical contexts within multiple settings.

Figure 5: Interactive Orrery device prototype, London, 2023.

Figure 6: Collecting the characters by hand-track, London, 2023.

5 PRELIMINARY EXPERIMENTS

5.1 Interaction test

Stage 1

In July 2023, the project's interaction mechanism combined physical devices with virtual reality. This stage elucidates the fundamental interaction between the moon and the windows in constructing a worldview. The physical devices were also conducted to control a virtual environment within Unity, where the moon dynamically interacts with the window. Through technical testing, the project successfully demonstrated initial effective interaction and construction of the virtual space. The efficiency of the connection between Arduino and Unity was verified, enabling dynamic movement of the moon in the virtual environment and real-time changes in its phases. Moreover, as the moon passes through a window, it emits light while smoothly transitioning to a new scene.

Stage 2

Before the Ars Electronica in Linz, Austria, 'Moonlit Windows' successfully developed its initial demo, showcasing a comprehensive user flow that introduces crucial interactions and guides players through various scenarios. The preliminary prototype of the Earth-Moon Rotation Box, an interactive physical device, has been completed to enable real-time interaction with the virtual reality environment. However, the interactive device of the project exhibits structural deficiencies and usability issues that necessitate improvement and updating. Additionally, conflicts arose between the data transfer ports of the physical device and the Oculus Quest2 VR headset.

Figure 7: Stage 1 Interaction test in Unity 3D and Arduino, London, 2023.

5.2 Ars Electronica 2023

From September 6 to 10, 2023, 'Moonlit Windows', a VR game inspired by 17th-century European oriental fantasies, debuted at the Ars Electronica in Linz, Austria. The project offered visitors a fully interactive experience featuring a vintage watercolour-style 3D environment with intriguing, exciting, and enjoyable collectable gameplay.

During the exhibition, the project received valuable feedback from audiences. The game's thematic elements and artistic effects garnered positive reviews, while constructive suggestions regarding VR interaction were made. Based on feedback from 89% of the audience, the captivating theme revolving around 17th-century European Oriental fantasies, explicitly focusing on the adventures of Italian Jesuit missionaries in China, received high praise due to its artistically stylised 3D art. The exquisite watercolour-like aesthetics conveyed a sense of historical context and deeply immersed the audience in the virtual world.

'Moonlit Windows' offered a combination of entertaining physical and virtual interactions; however, there were instances where the guidance for interaction could have been more explicit upon entering the VR space. Some feedback highlights the necessity of enhancing user guidance, ensuring audiences can easily comprehend how to interact with the game.

In conclusion, 'Moonlit Windows' at Ars Electronica garnered positive feedback, as well as valuable insights and constructive suggestions.

6 CONCLUSION

The interaction mechanics can be grounded in establishing a comprehensive worldview, while interactive elements can be tailored according to the thematic framework. In this context, Interaction design necessitates a focus on player-centricity to accomplish the

Figure 8: Exhibition at Arc Electronica, Austria, 2023.

objective of an immersive experience. The primary interaction mechanics should consider the player's role in the narrative and their pursued objectives. The player must perceive themselves as pivotal players in the story, with their choices and actions directly influencing its progression.

The surrealist aesthetic claims and representative works offer theoretical support and artistic references for developing virtual reality spaces, aligning with the concepts of automatism and subversion. By incorporating elements that encourage suggestive interactions within virtual reality environments, players are able to actively explore and engage with these elements, resulting in the creation of unconscious compositions through interconnecting simple, abstract visual elements that promote multiple associations.

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